

Increase Pod Density for K8s Worker Nodes

January 2025

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Agenda

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Business Problem

- Customer is using m5.large EC2 instances as the worker nodes for their EKS cluster.
- This instance type can have up to 3 ENI's and each interface can have up to 10 IP addresses. As a result can have maximum of $3 \times 9 = 27$ secondary IP addresses.
- Each node has enough CPU and memory resources available for running additional pods.
- However, all secondary IP addresses are exhausted, preventing additional pod scheduling.

Business Impact

- Limits application scalability.
- Causes underutilization of compute resources.
- Affects workload performance and reliability.
- Increases the cost of the infrastructure.

Pod Networking

- Every Pod gets its own IP address and containers in the same Pod share the Pod IP address.
- Pod networking is managed by VPC CNI in Secondary IP mode by default
- Pods communicate to other Pods without NAT across the nodes.

VPC CNI

VPC CNI Prefix Mode

- Allows assigning /28 (16 IP addresses) IPv4 prefixes instead of individual IPs. So for an instance with 3 ENIs, each 10 IP addresses we can have up to **3x9x16=432** IP addresses available for the Pods. One ENI is normally enough since we can have **9x16=144** IPs.
- From **version 1.9.0**, the CNI can assign IPv4 and IPv6 CIDRs instead of individual secondary IPs.
- Prefix mode is enabled by default for IPv6 clusters and is the only supported option. A /80 IPv6 prefix is assigned to a slot on an ENI.

Prefix Mode Implementation

Prerequisites:

- **Confirm if the VPC CNI is installed and running:**

```
kubectl get pods --selector=k8s-app=aws-node -n kube-system
```

- **Confirm the CNI version. The CNI version must be 1.9.0 or later**

```
kubectl describe daemonset aws-node --namespace kube-system | grep Image | cut -d "/" -f 2
```

Enable the CNI mode to Prefix mode:

```
kubectl set env daemonset aws-node -n kube-system ENABLE_PREFIX_DELEGATION=true
```

Prefix Mode Implementation

Verification:

- **Confirm if the VPC CNI is configured to run in prefix mode:**

```
kubectl get ds aws-node -o yaml -n kube-system | yq '.spec.template.spec.containers[].env'
```

```
[...]
```

```
- name: ENABLE_PREFIX_DELEGATION
```

```
  value: "true"
```

```
[...]
```

- **Confirm if a prefix assigned to the network interfaces of the worker nodes:**

```
aws ec2 describe-instances --filters "Name=tag-key,Values=eks:cluster-name" \
```

```
"Name=tag-value,Values=${EKS_CLUSTER_NAME}" \
```

```
--query 'Reservations[*].Instances[*.{InstanceId: InstanceId, Prefixes: NetworkInterfaces[*.Ipv4Prefixes[]}]'
```

Prefix Mode Implementation

```
[
  {
    "InstanceId": "i-0d1f7c060cf3ad0f4",
    "Prefixes": [
      {
        "Ipv4Prefix": "10.42.10.192/28"
      },
      {
        "Ipv4Prefix": "10.42.10.80/28"
      }
    ]
  },
  {
    "InstanceId": "i-0b47d3070af05c8b1",
    "Prefixes": [
      {
        "Ipv4Prefix": "10.42.10.16/28"
      },
      {
        "Ipv4Prefix": "10.42.10.160/28"
      }
    ]
  },
  {
    "InstanceId": "i-081b2a4d4e5f27991",
    "Prefixes": [
      {
        "Ipv4Prefix": "10.42.12.128/28"
      },
      {
        "Ipv4Prefix": "10.42.12.208/28"
      }
    ]
  }
]
```

Transition Strategy to Prefix Mode

Lessons Learned and Best Practices

- Monitoring IP Address Inventory
 - Ensures you always have visibility into IP address utilization and can avoid disruptions due to IP exhaustion. Use CNI Metrics Helper to monitor maximum available IPs.
- Deploying the VPC CNI EKS Add-On
 - New updates are provided by AWS and can be upgraded via console or CLI. Make sure during the upgrade preserve the existing settings:
aws eks update-addon --cluster-name my-cluster --addon-name vpc-cni --addon-version v1.19.0-eksbuild.1 --resolve-conflicts PRESERVE
- Using Similar Instance Types in Node Groups
 - The maximum pod count for an EKS cluster is constrained based on the instance type and VPC CNI mode with the lowest maximum pod count of the instances.
- Use VPC Subnet CIDR Reservations to reserve contiguous IP blocks for prefixes.
- Prefix mode reduces the need for multiple ENIs, streamlining IP allocation processes.
- Pods that existed before enabling prefix mode must be deleted and recreated to utilize the delegated prefixes.

Thank You

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January 2025